

Common Regional Market

July 2025

The **Western Balkans Agenda on Innovation, Research, Education, Culture, Youth and Sport** is a long-term strategy from the EU and the Western Balkans (WB) for cooperation with the region. It will contribute to the region’s economic and societal development and builds on three main pillars: Political, Thematic, and Regional.

The project POLICY ANSWERS monitors the implementation of the Western Balkans Agenda, and the broader context, progress and achievements are summarised in regular reports. In this Monitoring Card, you find the results of the third round of data collection during 2024 and the first months of 2025 in comparison to the data collected in the previous second monitoring round.

In terms of Common Regional Market, the monitoring focuses on the context indicator “Exports of goods in other WB economies as percentage of total exports” and various achievements outlined in the WB Agenda (see next page).

Achievements in a wider context of the Western Balkans Agenda

Source

Authors’ calculation based on <https://data.wiiw.ac.at/annual-database.html> (accessed 1 July 2025).

* This designation is without prejudice to positions on status, and is in line with UNSCR 1244/1999 and the ICJ Opinion on the Kosovo declaration of independence.

Indicator and overall assessment of the region	Preparation of S3 and support of their implementation			Increased investment in SMEs			Linking Western Balkans education and innovation activities					
	S3 milestones	Local S3 Support	S3 dialogue	Access to Finance (A2F) perception by Balkan Barometer	Macro Regional Strategies	Western Balkans Innovation Vouchers (WBIV)	Enterprise Europe Network and Erasmus for Young Entrepreneurs	Western Balkans in COST & EUREKA	Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) support	Infrastructure support	Reform Agenda milestones	
Albania	First S3 adopted	Increased number of events and publications	Increased number of events and participants	Moderate-level constraint	No new programmes joined	One Innovation Voucher awarded	No EIC events organised by EEN, beneficiaries not specified	Increased participation in COST, no EUREKA projects	Increased number of events, no information on publications provided	Increased number of R&I facilities, infrastructure support scheme in place	Green energy and business environment milestones partially achieved	
Bosnia and Herzegovina	S3 not adopted yet	Increased number of events and publications	No information provided	Moderate-level constraint	No new programmes joined	Three Innovation Vouchers awarded	EIC event organised, increased number of programmes' beneficiaries	Increased participation in COST, no information on EUREKA provided	Increased number of events and publications	Increased number of R&I facilities, infrastructure support scheme not in place	Not applicable for Bosnia and Herzegovina yet	
Kosovo	S3 not adopted yet	No information provided	No information provided	Moderate-level constraint	No new programmes joined	One Innovation Voucher awarded	EIC event organised, increased number of programmes' beneficiaries	Increased participation in COST, no participation in EUREKA	Increased number of events and publications	No new R&I facilities, infrastructure support scheme not yet in place	Business environment milestone partially achieved	
Montenegro	Second S3 under preparation	Increased number of events and publications	Increased number of events and participants	Moderate-level constraint	No new programmes joined	Eight Innovation Vouchers awarded	EIC event organised, increased number of programmes' beneficiaries	Increased participation in COST and EUREKA	No information provided	Increased number of R&I facilities, infrastructure support scheme not in place	No information provided	
North Macedonia	First S3 under implementation	Increased number of events and publications	In process of adoption of governance structure	Moderate-level constraint	No new programmes joined	Six Innovation Vouchers awarded	EIC events organised, increased number of programmes' beneficiaries	Increased participation in COST, no EUREKA projects	Increased number of events and publications	No new R&I facilities, infrastructure support scheme not yet in place	Green energy milestone achieved	
Serbia	First S3 under implementation	No new events reported, increased number of publications	Increased number of events and participants	Moderate-level constraint	No new programmes joined	Six Innovation Vouchers awarded	EIC events organised, increased number of programmes' beneficiaries	Increased participation in COST and EUREKA	Increased number of events and publications	Increased number of R&I facilities, infrastructure support scheme in place	Milestones not achieved	

Legend:

- On track or maintaining achievement
- Moderately improving, Challenges remain
- Stagnating, Significant challenges
- Decreasing, Major challenges
- Information not available

Highlights

- Three regions from the Western Balkans selected as Regional Innovation Valleys: Tuzla Kanton in Bosnia and Herzegovina, Montenegro and North Macedonia
- Collaborative grants for innovation managed by the Innovation Fund of Montenegro certified for the Plug-In scheme to the EIC Accelerator
- New phase of the Common Regional Market Action Plan 2025–2028 signed by Western Balkans leaders

